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Perceptions of Riverside Inhabitants on Riverbank Waste Disposal and its Attendant Effects: Case Study of River Bali, Bali LGA, Taraba State

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ABSTRACT

The study investigates the perception of the environmental impact of waste disposal by the Riverside inhabitants of River Bali, Bali Local Government Area of Taraba State, Nigeria. The study further identified; method of waste disposal within the study area, influence of waste disposal method on open space and streams, environmental problems associated with waste deposited on river channel. Primary data for the study were generated through questionnaire administration. Fifty (50) questionnaires were systematically distributed in each of the selected sampled locations that included; Anguwan Kundi, Kwararafa, Nainawa, Mahanga and Daniya settlements. Simple percentages and Tables were employed for data analysis. It was observed that wastes are being flushed into streams/River and thereby affects the odor, taste and coloration of water quality. Flooding activities identified in this area is majorly caused by indiscriminate waste disposal that blocks water drainages. The study therefore recommends provision of waste management strategy that will ensure neatness of environment and avoid pollution of water with effective refuse collection and disposal system within the study area and the related environments.

Keywords: River, waste, waste management, waste disposal, pollution.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

One of the prominent components of man's environment is the river that flows gently within its natural course. It serves as the source of water for many purposes such as agricultural and domestic. River provides both defense and transportation means for humans, yet when the volume of water in a river smells due to disposal of indecent elements, such as wastes, it then starts to pose a threat to its nearby

inhabitants (Rosenbaun, 2013). Wastes are unwanted or useless materials generated from the combined residential, industrial, and commercial activities of a given area. Solid wastes could be categorized according to its origin (domestic, industrial, commercial, construction or institutional, containing material like the glass, metal, plastic paper, etc.) or according to its hazard potential (toxic, non-toxin, flammable, radioactive, inflections, etc. (Lateef *et al.*, 2015). Municipal solid waste (MSW) is described as domestic as well as commercial waste that account for a relatively small part of the total solid waste stream in developing countries (Anjana *et al.*, 2012). A municipal solid waste dumpsite is not a benign repository of discarded material; it is a biochemically active unit where toxic substances are leached or created from combinations of non-toxic precursors and gradually released into the surrounding environment over a period of decades (Karatzas, *et al.*, 2006). Over the last couple of decades there has been an increase in the effect of environmental pollution on the health of the populace due to the improper disposal of waste in rivers. Improper waste disposal has become a major environmental concern affecting not only the health of the general public (health hazards) but also the surrounding environment (environmental hazards). The most prominent result of health hazards is the wide spread of communicable diseases like cholera (Hoorweg, *et al.*, 1999). Additionally, waste can become a major problem on human health especially where it is not well managed, unregulated growth of urban areas and inadequate infrastructural facilities for collection, transporting, treating and disposal of waste have all contributed to the increase in pollution level across many cities. The heterogeneous mixture of plastics, cloths, metals and organic solution which are inevitable products of production and consumption are also on the increase due to urbanization, population growth and poverty. These give room for indiscriminate discharge of solid and sewage waste into river channels thereby causing serious flooding and obnoxious smells which peril the lives of inhabitants living along river channels (NSDWQ, 2019). Therefore, this study aimed to investigate the impacts of the uncontrolled disposal of waste into River Bali and its consequences on the surrounding dwellers by identifying the waste composition, characteristics and the inconveniences pose by these actions. The study also assesses the perception of the impact of waste disposal in River Bali and its attendant effects on the surroundings dwellers.

2.0 Literature review

Waste is regarded as any unwanted, undesirable or any material which the owner regard it as no longer valuable, it is an inevitable and inherent product of social, economic and cultural life. Its composition and volume largely depend on consumption patterns as well as the industrial and economic structures of the people in place (Ahmed *et al.*, 2016).

According to Kadam *et al.*, (2016), waste can be classified into solid waste and liquid waste.

- i. **Solid waste:** is regarded as any garbage, refuse or rubbish that emanate from homes and other places around residential, these include the old car tires, old newspapers, broken furniture, and unwanted electronics and may sometimes include food waste.
- ii. **Municipal solid waste:** Municipal solid waste comprises of the household waste, construction as well as demolition debris, sanitation residue, and waste from streets. Mainly, this type of garbage is generated from residential as well as commercial complexes.
- iii. **Hazardous waste:** constitute any waste material, whether liquid, solid, or gaseous, that is toxic, corrosive, reactive, or flammable that endangers human health or the environment. It comes from both domestic and industrial sources, and it needs to be managed carefully to avoid contaminating the air, soil, and water.
- iv. **Liquid waste:** Liquid waste is the waste generated in the kitchen, bathroom and laundry and also called the grey water. While the waste water generated in the toilet is called black water, it may contain harmful pathogen.

The indiscriminate disposal of waste, both liquid and solid, adversely affects the immediate human environment by degrading the natural phenomena hence, exerting health risk to exposed population (Sunitha *et al.*, 2023). Nigeria as the most populous country in Africa with a continuous growing

population of above 200 million people. The growth of population in urban areas is been characterized by continuous increase in the amounts of waste generated (Burmamu *et al.*, 2014).

The complexities of waste which modern civilization produce is directly related to the living standards, socio-economic and cultural attributes of that particular environment. It also asserted that waste streams could be characterized by their sources, type of waste (solid, liquid, or gaseous states) produced as well as generation rate and composition. This also classified the waste into eight namely; residential, industrial, commercial, institutional, constructional, demolition, municipal services, process and agriculture (Adeniran *et al.*, 2014). Disposal of solid waste is essential in the management of solid waste; this is required to avoid environmental pollution and health problems. However, most wastes disposal sites are found commonly along the outskirts of urban areas, major/minor roadside, as well as nearby water bodies open spaces (Akinola, 2016). Inappropriate disposal of wastes leads to contamination of surface and ground water through leachate, soil contamination via direct waste contact, air pollution by burning of wastes, spreading of diseases by different vectors like birds, insects and rodents, or uncontrolled re-lease of methane during anaerobic decomposition of organic component of the waste (Katarzyna, 2018).

Dumpsites are areas where waste materials are disposed and are viewed as the oldest form of waste treatment (Oyelami *et al.*, 2013). Historically, dumpsites have been the most common method of unorganized waste disposal in many places around the world. Most dumpsites are located within the vicinity of living communities and wetlands. Local dumpsites are often not lined nor basement prepared for selective absorption of toxic substances (Onoharigho *et al.*, 2022). Which makes it prone to release of pollutant, leachate and obnoxious gases to nearby water, and air in the surroundings (Chikaodili *et al.*, 2017). Wet waste or organic component of the waste decomposes and releases a bad odour that affects the people living around such dumpsites (Ibe *et al.*, 2021). Additionally, dumpsites found close to residential areas are found to be suitable sites for scavengers, animals feeding (dogs, pets) which could carry diseases with them to homesteads around (Ibrahim, 2011). Groundwater pollution occurs when hazardous substances come into contact with and dissolve in the water and soaked into the soil (Kurwadkar *et al.*, 2020). If rain or surface water encounters contaminated soil while seeping into the ground, it can become polluted and can carry the pollution from the soil to the groundwater (Sidiropoulos, 2024). Underground water aquifers can also become contaminated when hazardous liquid substances soak themselves down through the soil into the groundwater sources. This, therefore, calls for stringent sustainable urban solid waste management practices (Andersen *et al.* 2011).

2.1 Waste management practice

The need for waste management is to gain an understanding of waste management planning concepts, frameworks, strategies, and also components that are emerging in the field. The sorting of waste is essential as the amount of waste being generated today causes immense problem (Amasuomo and Baird, 2016). In fact, it is believed that a larger portion can be recycled, a part of it can be converted to compost and also only a smaller portion of it is really waste that has no use and has to be discarded (Bagban, *et al.*, 2016). Waste management is one of the most poorly rendered services by municipal authorities in developing countries as the systems applied are unscientific, outdated (Kumar *et al.*, 2017). The waste management practice is inefficient because of the low economic returns from the trade with an increase in the global population and the rising demand for food, water, and other resources, the amount of waste generated by each urban household increases daily (Zaman, 2015).

2.2 Types of wastes management practice

2.2.1 Waste segregation

Waste segregation can be defined as the process of identifying, classifying, dividing and sorting of garbage and waste products in an effort to reduce, reuse and recycle materials (Rupali, *et al.*, 2016).

2.2.2 Wate incineration

Incineration is a one of the disposal methods of solid waste in which waste is subjected to combustion of organic substance which contained in the waste and also high temperature treatment system as known as “thermal treatment. It converts the waste into ash and gaseous products. This method also useful for

disposal of residue of solid waste management as well as solid residue from waste water management and also this process reduces the volumes of solid waste to 20 to 30 percent of the original volume. Incineration is used in both on a small scale by individuals and on a large scale by industry. This method also recognized as a practical method of disposing of certain hazardous waste materials including biological medical waste. Incineration method commonly used in countries such as Japan where land is scarcer, as these facilities generally do not require as much area as landfills.

2.2.3 Landfill

Landfill is most common method of waste treatment around the world. Landfill consists of burying the waste and also remains a common practice in most countries. If landfills are properly designed and well-managed, then a landfill can be a hygienic as well as relatively inexpensive method of disposing of waste. In older days, poorly managed landfills and waste dumped in open areas created a number of adverse environmental impacts like wind-blown litter, attraction of vermin, as well as generation of liquid leachate. Landfills generate gas mostly composed of methane and carbon dioxide which kills the surface vegetation and also is a greenhouse gas.

2.2.4 Recycling

Recycling means the materials from which the new items are made or the materials which can be reprocessed into new products (Liu *et al.*, 2023). Firstly, waste material is collected separately from general waste using dedicated bins like dry waste, wet waste and plastic and collection vehicles, a procedure also known as kerbside collection (Hamad *et al.*, 2013).

2.3 Impact of indiscriminate waste disposal

One of the main aspects of concern associated with uncontrolled waste disposal and treatment is environmental pollution either on lands, air, or water (Burmamu *et al.*, 2014). For instance, groundwater pollution occurs when hazardous substances came in contact pollutants, dissolve and soaked into the soil (Jerie, 2016). If rain or surface water encounters contaminated soil while seeping into the ground, it can become polluted and can carry the pollution from the soil to the groundwater (Abubakar *et al.*, 2021). Groundwater can also become contaminated when hazardous liquid substances are been poured directly on to the surface soil or water body, which will subsequently leached into the groundwater sources (Ziraba *et al.*, 2016).

2.3 Human health impact of uncontrolled waste disposal

2.3.1 Infections

Improper disposal of waste can lead to the spread of infections and diseases. For instance, hospital waste; may carry harmful pathogens that can cause infections if not disposed of properly (Abubakar *et al.*, 2021)

2.3.2 Toxins

Some menstrual products contain chemicals and toxins that can harm the human body when exposed to them for prolonged periods (Exposto and Sujaya, 2021). For instance, dioxins, a toxic byproduct of the bleaching process used in manufacturing pads and tampons, can accumulate in the body over time and have been linked to various health issues such as cancer and endometriosis (Dubey *et al.*, 2024).

2.3.3 Occupational hazards

The workers who handle menstrual waste can be exposed to harmful chemicals and pathogens, putting them at risk of contracting infections and other health problems (Jerie, 2016). Gowda *et al.* (2023), found that workers who handle menstrual waste are at risk of skin irritation, respiratory problems, and infections.

3.0 MATERIAL AND METHODS

3.1 Description of the study area

River Bali, Taraba State, Nigeria, a tributary of the River Benue. River Bali is at latitude of 8° 34' 0" N and longitude of 10° 15' 0" E. River Bali takes its source from the high altitude of the Atlantic Ocean and hills on the Nigeria-Cameroon border in the Mid-Eastern part of Taraba state and flows westwards, covering a distance of about 265km before entering the River Benue. The major economic activities along

River, include fishing and farming of rice, millet, Guinea corn, and groundnut (Akogun, 1999). It is the largest local Government in Taraba State, with an estimated land area of 11,540 km Based on the results of the 2006 National Population Census, Bali local Government had a population of about 211,024 persons (NPC, 2006). It has a tropical climate marked by two seasons; dry and rainy seasons. The rainy season starts around April and ends November occasionally, with 1350 – 1500mm rainfall annually. The dry season is from December to March. The major ethnic groups in the area include; Jibawa, Tiv, Chamba, Fulani, Hausa, Itchen etc., the major occupation of the inhabitants is farming, fishing and nomadism.

3.2 Method

In order to determine the assess the perception of the riverside dwellers on the impacts of the riverside waste disposal, this study conducted qualitative research utilizing only primary data from the sampled respondents. Descriptive survey was adopted as this study’s research design, a structure questionnaire was utilized as this study’s data collection instrument. The population for this study comprises of the inhabitants around River Bali with Fifty (50) respondents selected randomly among the residents nearby the river side, comprising of both male and female. The sample size for this study was determined using Taro Yemane formular as expressed

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where n is the sample size, N is population and “e” is the significant level (95%). Using the above formular, $n = \frac{50}{1 + 50 (0.05)^2} = 40$ approximately. The data obtained for this study was analyzed using simple percentage which were presented in table for interpretation and deductive reasoning.

4.0 RESULTS

4.1 Demographic information of respondents

The demographic distribution of this study’s participants is presented in table 4.1, the shows the gender, age, marital status, educational qualification of the respondents and their percentages.

Table 4.1 Demographic characteristics of Respondents

Gender	Respondents	Percentages
Males	30	60%
Females	20	40%
Total	50	100%
Age	Respondents	Percentages
18- 25	20	40%
27 – Above	30	60%
Total	50	100%
Marital Status	Respondents	Percentages
Married	35	70%
Single	15	30%
Total	50	100%
Educational Qualification	Respondents	Percentage
SSCE	7	14%
NCE/OND	33	66%

HND/B.Sc.	10	20%
Total	50	100%

Source: (Field Survey, 2024).

Table 4.1 presents the demographic characteristics of the sampled participants for this study, the gender distribution of 50 respondents showed that 60% were males, while 40% were females. The age distribution of the respondents showed that 40% of the participants were between 18-25 years of age while 60% were above 27 years. From the above table, one can conclusively say that out of 50 respondents 70% were married while 15 accounting for 30% were single. The table above depicts that 14% percent were with Senior School Certificate (SSCE), 66% were those with NCE/OND Certificates while 20% percent are those with B.Sc. and HND Certificates of Degree.

Table 4.2 constitute the responses of the sample inhabitants around the river; the question seeks to sampled their opinion on the impacts of the indiscriminate waste disposal in River.

4.2 Perception and knowledge of the effects of waste disposal in the river

Table 4.2 provides the perception of the impacts of indiscriminate waste disposal in the river by the riverside dwellers.

Table 4.2: Indiscriminate dumping of waste in River Bali lead to adverse environmental pollution and health hazard.

Option	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Total
Response	20	15	5	4	6	50
Percentage	40%	30%	10%	8%	12%	100%

Source: (Field work, 2024).

Table 4.2, shows that 20 respondents strongly agreed that indiscriminate waste disposal causes environmental pollution which represented by 40%, 15 respondents agreed which represent 30%, 5 respondents was undecided and represents by 10% followed by 4 respondents disagreed that is 8% while 6 respondents represented by 12% strongly disagreed. It can be deduced from the above table that the highest percentage of the respondents agree that indiscriminate waste disposal causes environmental pollution.

Research question two: *What are the different kinds of wastes products mostly dump in River Bali, Bali LGA of Taraba state?*

Table: 4.6: The various kinds of wastes products being dump or dispose in River Bali include; solid and liquid wastes such as; plastic wastes, leather, rubber, human/animal wastes and remains of animals.

Options	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
Response	33	12	0	3	2	50
Percentage	66%	24%	0%	6%	4%	100%

Source: (Fieldwork, 2024).

As shown in Table 4.6, Thirty-three (33) respondents strongly agreed representing 66%, 12 respondents agreed representing 24%, 0 respondents are undecided which is 0% and 3 respondents disagree which is 6% were 2 respondents strongly disagree with 4%.

Research question three: *What are the possible solutions toward the effects of wastes disposal in River Bali, Bali LGA of Taraba state?*

Table 4.7: Provisions of adequate measures like; creating awareness, discouraging indiscriminate dumping of waste in River Bali, educating people on the proper means of waste disposal around the Riverine area and government should create policy on waste disposal.

Options	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
Response	24	11	5	4	6	50
Percentage	48%	22%	10%	8%	12%	100%

Source: (Fieldwork, 2024).

The Table above indicated that 24 respondents strongly agreed represented by 48% of the respondents, 11 respondents agreed represented by 22%, 5 respondents undecided represented by 10%, 4 respondents disagreed represented by 8% while 6 respondents represented by 12% of the respondents strongly disagreed. Hence the highest percentage of the respondents agreed that the possible solutions to the menace of waste disposal includes; creating awareness, government policy and proper waste disposal in the Riverine area.

4.2 DISCUSSION

Based on this study’s findings, there is a lack of proper waste disposal and segregation of sanitary waste among the populace. Open disposal into the river was considered as the main waste disposal method adopted by the resident. This finding is consistent and corroborates Vinti & Vaccari, (2022) that revealed riverside waste disposal as the most common waste disposal approach adopted by riverside dwellers and low-income urban context. The most dominant waste includes polythene bags, plastic bottles (for beverages), empty cartons, and baby diapers. River sate dumping was associated mostly with some careless homestead members and restaurant owners neighboring rivers in the community. This was found to be done by people who lacked domestic dumpsite or dust bin and those who lacked garbage collection bin in their houses.

Additionally, this study revealed that solid waste was associated with water pollution in River Bali water, leachate from nearby dumpsites was also seen to cause water pollution through runoff. This finding conforms with Burmamu *et al.*, (2014) who indicated that leachate formed from water that trickled through the solid waste dumpsites and landfills in Jimeta-Yola during rainy season collected in the surface and ground water. This comes with increase in biological oxygen demand (BOD), pH, total hardness, calcium, magnesium, sodium concentration, total dissolved solid, nitrate and total alkalinity, which does not only affect aquatic ecosystem health but also humans that consume this water directly from the rivers and nearby local wells. The wastes dumped in rivers were seen to obstruct and sealed water channels and shallow streams leading to flooding particularly during rainy season while making the town untidy. This also supports Okereke *et al.* (2016) who indicated that uncontrolled waste disposal has a potential of causing flood in urban centers. This means that the cause of this flooding should been avoided by employing proper waste management practice. Shekdar *et al.* (1991) observed that, polythene bags are not biodegradable and can remain in soils/water for many years without decomposing which creates eye sore in the soil environment. In the current study, we observed that, land filling and open dumping of wastes were associated with spreading of non-biodegradable waste transfers of polythene bags, plastics, glasses and metallic sheets into the soil and water bodies. These were found to reduce soil air and water movement as well as reducing soil living organisms which also reduced soil fertility hence degradation.

5.0 SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary

This study examined the perceptions of the environmental impact of waste dumping in River Bali, Bali Local Government area of Taraba State. Specifically, the following has constituted the specific objectives of the study: to identify the impact of waste dump in River Bali, Bali LGA of Taraba State; to identify the various kinds of wastes products that are mostly being dispose in River Bali; to also provide recommendations on the challenges posed by waste disposal in River Bali, Bali LGA of Taraba State. Through the analysis of the data collected for the purpose of the study answers to the stated research questions were provided; what are the impact of waste dump in River Bali? What are the various kinds of wastes products being deposited in River Bali? What are the possible solutions towards the effects of waste disposal in River Bali? From the array of related literature reviewed on this study and analysis on the questionnaire result, using simple percentage and frequency distribution, it is now understandable, as it remains conspicuous that indiscriminate disposal of waste products causes a lot of harmful effect to the environment and human health. Lastly, more awareness on the harmful effect of indiscriminate waste disposal is expected to enlighten the dwellers of the Riverine area.

5.2 Conclusion

The study aimed at carrying out a complete assessment of the impact of environmental waste dump in River Bali, Bali LGA of Taraba State. The study revealed that wastes disposed into river/stream channels indiscriminately resulted into drainage blockage, disastrous flooding, infrastructural degradation, stream/river pollution and underground water contamination. Thus, sustainable management of waste is needed to correct these environmental anomalies that impact lives and properties. Waste management facilities helped to learn from previous experiences and in identifying most of the negative impacts, which are mainly related to operational inadequacies, resulting from the lack of environmental awareness, lack of waste separation, poor technical qualifications of workers, and poor facility management. According to Sanko *et al.* (2013), recycling solid waste products was resorted to as a solution to limited raw material (raw material substitution), this is because, solid wastes are cheaper and easier to re-use in factories than raw material. In addition, recycling was seen as a savior of environment of accumulating solid waste.

5.3 Recommendations

This study, therefore, recommend that:

- i. Bali Local Government authorities should make use of local media houses to sensitize people on how best they can dispose their wastes and should promote re-use (recycling) by increasing on the incentives of collection, sorting and assembling recyclable non-biodegradable wastes.
- ii. The authorities should also ensure that, dump sites are located in isolated areas of at least 20 meters away from the nearest homesteads to minimize effects of the solid wastes on the environment such as flies and vermin encroaching on homesteads and causing diseases as well as limiting the bad smell from these rotting wastes.
- iii. The authorities should ensure regular multi-stage collection strategy to empty collection centers in time before they over-fill and block drainage channels. This can be done by recruiting and training adequate staff for scavenging, composting and recycling of solid wastes.
- iv. The authorities need to invest in promoting awareness and advancing education to the Town dwellers on the effects of improper waste disposal practices through knowledge and skills sharing platforms such as training, conferences, seminars, which can best be done by decentralizing them to the smallest political unit such as community level. This will aid in minimizing the scattering of waste disposed in open spaces.
- v. On this ground, the study suggests that there should be waste management strategy to ensure neatness of environment and avoid pollution from wastes through the provision of less strenuous and effective refuse collection and disposal system within the study area and the related environment.

6.0 REFERENCES

- Abdus-Salam, N., Ibrahim, M.S. and Fatoyinbo, F.T. (2011). Dumpsites in Lokoja, Nigeria. A silent pollution zone for underground water. *Journal of Waste management and Bio-resources technology*, 3(1), pp. 21-30.
- Abubakar, I.R., Maniruzzaman, K.M., Dano, U.L., AlShihri, F.S., AlShammari, M.S., Ahmed, S.M.S., Al-Gehlani, W.A.G. and Alrawaf, T.I. (2022). Environmental sustainability impacts of solid waste management practices in the global South. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 19(19), p.12717.
- Adeniran, A.A., Adewole, A.A. and Olofa, S.A. (2014). Impact of solid waste management on Ado -Ekiti property values. *Journal of Civil and Environmental Research*, 6(9), pp. 29-38.
- Agarwal, A., Singhmar, A., Kulshrestha, M., and Mittal, A. K. (2005). Municipal solid waste recycling and associated markets in Delhi, India. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 44(1), pp. 73-90.
- Akinola, P. (2016). Investigation of the implementation and effectiveness of electronic waste management in Nigeria. *Model Earth System and Environment*, 2(100), pp. 1 - 6.
- Akogun, O.B. (1999). Eye lesions, blindness and visual impairment in the Taraba River Valley, Nigeria and their relation to on Cho cercal microfilariae in skin. *Acta Tropica*, 51(1992), pp. 143-149.
- Amasuomo, E. and Baird, J. (2016). The concept of waste and waste management. *Journal of Management and Sustainability*, 6, p.88.
- Andersen, J. K A. Boldrin, T.H. Christensen, and Scheutz, C. (2011). Mass balances and lifecycle inventory of home composting of organic waste. *Waste Management*, 31, pp. 1934-1942.
- Bagban, M.S., Kadam, P.R., Ingale, S.A. and Kad, R.S. (2016). An insight into Different Waste Types and Waste Segregation Methods. *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IRJET)*, 3(4), pp. 2060 – 2063.
- Burmamu, B. R., Law, P. L., Aliyu, H. H., and Ibrahim, Y. (2014). Environmental impacts and management strategies of solid waste disposal in Jimeta-Yola, Nigeria. *International Journal of Environmental Engineering Science and Technology Research*, 2(3), pp. 3-7.
- Chikaodili, E.B., Iheanyichukwu, O.A., Kelechi, N.O. and Ikechukwu, N.E. (2017). Geochemical and bacteriological analyses of water resources prone to contamination from solid waste dumpsites in Imo State, Southeastern Nigeria.
- Dubey, D.K., Agarwal, S., Yadav, M.P., Goswami, A. and Ravat, A. (2024). The study of the effects of improper hazardous waste disposal on ecosystems. *Indian Journal of Science and Research*, 4(2), pp.130-136.
- Elijah M.I and John, E. (2019). Planktonic Composition of River Taraba in Bali Town, Taraba State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Science, Engineering and Technology*, 6(8), pp. 2348 – 7968.
- Exposto, L.A.S. and Sujaya, I.N. (2021). The impacts of hazardous and toxic waste management: a systematic review. *Interdisciplinary Social Studies*, 1(2), pp.103-123.
- Foday, P. S, Xiangbin. Y, Quangyen, T. (2013). Environmental and Health Impact of Solid Waste Disposal in Developing Cities: A Case. Study of Granville Brook Dumpsite, Freetown, SierraLeone. *Journal of Environmental Protection*, 4, pp. 665 – 670. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4236/jep.2013.47076>.
- Goorah, S. S. D., Esmiyot, M. L. I., and Boojhawon, R. (2009). The health impact of nonhazardous solid waste disposal in a community: the case of the Mare Chicose landfill in Mauritius. *Journal of Environmental Health*, 72(1), pp. 48 - 55.
- Gowda, B., Gurusiddappa, L.H. and Kalikeri, S. (2023). Study on occupational health hazards of municipal solid waste workers-a review. *World Journal of Environmental Biosciences*, 12(1-2023), pp.24-31.

- Hamad, K., Kaseem, M. and Deri, F. (2013). Recycling of waste from polymer materials: An overview of the recent works. *Polymer degradation and stability*, 98(12), pp.2801-2812.
- Hoornweg D (1999). Solid waste management in Asia. The international Bank for Recombination and development, World Bank report, pp. 100-167.
- Ibe, F.C., Opara, A.I., Amaobi, C.E. and Ibe, B.O. (2021). Environmental risk assessment of the intake of contaminants in aquifers in the vicinity of a reclaimed waste dumpsite in Owerri municipal, Southeastern Nigeria. *Applied Water Science*, 11(2), pp.24.
- Israel, G.D. (1992). Determining Sample Size. University of Florida Cooperative Extension Service, Institute of Food and Agriculture Sciences, EDIS, Florida.
- Jerie, S. (2016). Occupational risks associated with solid waste management in the informal sector of Gweru, Zimbabwe. *Journal of Environmental and Public Health*, 2016(1), pp.9024160.
- Kalama. N.K (2016). Effects of solid waste management projects on the welfare of local community. A case of solid waste management projects in Mombasa city, Kenya. M.A thesis in project planning and management, university of Nairobi.
- Katarzyna. G. (2018). The environmental impact of solid waste management systems. *E35 web of conferences*, 31(4), pp. 793-9.
- Kumar, S., Smith, S.R., Fowler, G., Velis, C., Kumar, S.J., Arya, S., Rena, Kumar, R. and Cheeseman, C. (2017). Challenges and opportunities associated with waste management in India. *Royal Society open science*, 4(3), p.160764.
- Kurwadkar, S., Kanel, S.R. and Nakarmi, A. (2020). Groundwater pollution: Occurrence, detection, and remediation of organic and inorganic pollutants. *Water Environment Research*, 92(10), pp.1659-1668.
- Liu, K., Tan, Q., Yu, J. and Wang, M. (2023). A global perspective on e-waste recycling. *Circular Economy*, 2(1), pp.100028.
- Muhib, M. I., Akter, R., Kabir, M. H., Rayhan, M. S. and Khan, M.S. A. (2021). Disseminating the biomedical waste Generation scenario during covid-19: An Overview from the lower middle-income Country Bangladesh. *American International Journal of Nursing Education and Practice*, 2(1), pp. 7-14.
- National Emergency Management Agency (2012). The state of environment report for Uganda, NEMA, Kampala, Uganda. Environmental and Socio-Economic Impact Assessment of Solid Waste Management Practices.
- Lateef, T.A., Eluwole, A. B. and Adewa, D.J. (2015). Geoelectrical assessment of the impact of the Ilokun dumpsite, Ado-Ekiti Southwestern Nigeria, on surrounding groundwater Aquifers. *International Letters of Natural Sciences*, 40, pp. 41-47.
- Nigerian Standard for Quality Drinking Water (2007). Nigerian standard for drinking water quality. Nigeria Industrial Standard, Approve by Standard Organization of Nigeria Governing Council. ICS 13. 060, 20, pp. 15-45.
- Nworgu, B. G. (2006). Educational research (2nd ed). Enugu: University Trust Publishers.
- Nyakaana, J. B. (1997). Solid waste management in urban centers. A case of Kampala city– Uganda. *The east African geographical review*, 19(1), pp. 33-43.
- Ogbonna, D. N., Amangabara, G. T. and Ekere, T. O. (2007). Urban solid waste generation in Port Harcourt metropolis and its implications for waste management. *International Journal of Management of Environmental Quality*, (1)18, pp.71-88.
- Okereke, J. N., Ogidi, O. I. and Obasi, K. O. (2016). Environmental and health impact of industrial wastewater effluents in Nigeria-A Review. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Biological Sciences*, 3(6), pp. 55-67.
- Onoharigho, F.O., Akpodimo, E.O. and Edo, G.I. (2022). The effect of uncontrolled dumping of solid waste on groundwater in Osun State, Nigeria. *Fine Chemical Engineering*, pp. 156 -170.

- Osondu, I.N., Floyd, G. and Samake, S. (2004). The Use and Application of GIS in Third World Development programs. Association of Third World Studies 22nd. Annual Conference, Macon, Georgia October 7 – 9.
- Oyelami, A.C., Aladejana, J.A. and Agbede, O.O. (2013). Assessment of the impact of open waste dumpsites on groundwater quality: a case study of the Onibu-Eja dumpsite, southwestern Nigeria. *Procedia Earth and planetary science*, 7, pp.648-651.
- Papadopoulou, M., Karatzas, G. and Bougloukou, G. (2006). Numerical modeling of the environment impacts of landfill long age on groundwater quality a field application. *Greece journal of Science*, 5(3), pp. 67-78.
- Sunitha, B.K., Roopa, K.V., Pallapati, D. and Esha, M. (2023). Study on waste segregation and its impact on environment. *International Journal of Development Research*, 13(3), pp. 62204-62211.
- Pushpentra, S.B., Anjana, S., Akhilesh, K.P., Priyanka, P. and Abhishek, K.A. (2012) Physico-chemical analysis of groundwater near municipal solid waste dumping sites in Jabalpur. *International Journal of Plant, Animal and Environmental Sciences* 2(1), pp. 217-222.
- Rosenbaun, H.C. (2013). Chemical Pollution and Nutrient Pollution/Contaminants-Urban, Available at: www.environment.gov.au/archive.
- Sankoh, F. P., Yan, X., and Tran, Q. (2013). Environmental and health impact of solid waste disposal in developing cities: a case study of Granville brook dumpsite, Freetown, Sierra Leone. *Journal of Environmental Protection*, 4(7), pp.665-670.
- Shekdar, A. V., Krishnaswamy, K. N., Tikekar, V. G., and Bhide, A. D. (1991). Long-term planning for solid waste management in India. *Waste management and research*, 9(6), pp. 511-523.
- Sidiropoulos, P. (2024). Groundwater Pollution: Sources, Mechanisms, and Prevention. *Hydrology*, 11(7), pp.98.
- Turyahabwe, R., Mulabbi, A., Asaba, J., and Olowo, M. (2021). Ecological Responses of Macroinvertebrates to an In-Stream Ecosystem Restoration Technique in a Tropical Stream in Eastern Uganda. *East African Journal of Environment and Natural Resources*, 3(1), pp. 129-144.
- Vinti, G., and Vaccari, M. (2022). Solid waste management in rural communities of developing countries: An overview of challenges and opportunities. *Clean Technologies*, 4(4), pp. 1138-1151. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cleantechnol4040069>.
- World Bank. (2010). The World Bank Annual Report 2010: Year in Review. World Bank Annual Report. Washington, DC. World Bank. <https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/handle/10986/5906> License: CC BY 3.0 IGO.
- Zaman, A.U. (2015). A comprehensive review of the development of zero waste management: lessons learned and guidelines. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 91, pp.12-25.
- Ziraba, A.K., Haregu, T.N. and Mberu, B. (2016). A review and framework for understanding the potential impact of poor solid waste management on health in developing countries. *Archives of Public Health*, 74(1), pp.55.